

1 **Activation of Arhgef39 by HPV16 E7.**

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6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of Arhgef39 by
9 HPV16 HPV E7.

10 Citations

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15 are essential receptor tyrosine kinase effectors for Rac1-dependent cell motility in human lung
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